

Teaching Methodologies Present in the New Mexican School and Their Educational Impact

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Resumen

Ante la implementación del modelo educativo 2022 en educación básica en México, se realiza la presente investigación, la cual tiene como problema principal la búsqueda de las metodologías que son utilizadas en la educación actual y su contraste con los principios de la Nueva Escuela Mexicana (NEM), analizando cuál es la transición de una metodología tradicional a una constructivista, y cuales existen dentro del aula. El objetivo de la investigación es analizar la implementación de las metodologías didácticas propuestas por la NEM y su influencia en la práctica docente en la educación básica. La metodología empleada es de enfoque cualitativo, utilizando la aplicación de técnicas como entrevistas semiestructuradas, por medio del enfoque de la fenomenología, enfocado hacia las categorías de análisis de barreras, dificultades, fortalezas, metodologías y contraste político. El procesamiento de la información se realizó por medio del software Atlas.Ti 9.^a edición. Los resultados evidencian tanto avances como desafíos en la adopción de las metodologías promovidas por la NEM, destacando la necesidad de una formación continua para los docentes y un acompañamiento efectivo. Las conclusiones subrayan la importancia de articular la teoría educativa con la práctica en el aula, promoviendo una educación que responda a las necesidades del contexto actual.

Palabras clave: Aprendizaje significativo, educación básica, práctica docente y metodología de la enseñanza.

Abstract

In light of the implementation of the 2022 educational model in basic education, this research is conducted. Its main objective is to identify the methodologies used in current education and compare them with the principles of the New Mexican School (NEM). This research

analyzes the transition from a traditional to a constructivist methodology, as well as those existing in the classroom. The objective of this research is to analyze the implementation of the teaching methodologies proposed by the NEM and their influence on teaching practice in basic education. The methodology employed is qualitative, utilizing techniques such as semi-structured interviews and a phenomenological approach, focusing on the categories of analysis of barriers, difficulties, strengths, methodologies, and political contrast. Data processing was performed using Atlas.Ti 9th edition software. The results show progress and challenges in the adoption of the methodologies promoted by the NEM, highlighting the need for ongoing teacher training and effective support. The conclusions underscore the importance of coordinating educational theory with classroom practice, promoting an education that responds to the needs of the current context.

Keywords: Meaningful learning, basic education, teaching practice and teaching methodology.

Introduction

In the context of contemporary primary education, Mexico faces a significant challenge due to the emergence of new pedagogical methodologies. This situation requires moving away from traditional educational practices and embracing adaptation and innovation that respond to modern educational needs. In the 21st century, primary education in Mexico has undergone a major transformation through the introduction of the Nueva Escuela Mexicana (New Mexican School, NEM), which implements a “new” educational policy aimed at transforming the national education system.

Within the framework of the New Mexican School (NEM), proposed in 2019, the Secretariat of Public Education (SEP, 2022, p. 11) defines it as “an initiative to renew the country’s educational approach, guiding it toward a humanistic perspective based on equity, inclusion, respect for diversity, and the development of critical and scientific thinking.” Based on this premise, the model promotes student-centered education, collaborative learning, and the integration of new digital technologies. However, the implementation of this model and its foundational methodologies faces obstacles arising from deficiencies and from traditional pedagogical practices still prevalent in current classroom contexts.

The implementation of the NEM entails several major challenges, such as:

- a) continuous teacher training;
- b) the availability of resources to adopt these new methodologies; and
- c) the lack of infrastructure in both rural and marginalized communities, which limits opportunities for effective educational innovation. Moreover, within the introduction of a new methodological framework, one of the main challenges lies in the resistance to change, resistance to new models and pedagogies that promote alternative forms of learning.

The core problem addressed in this study is the identification of methodologies currently used in the educational context and their contrast with the NEM's approach, emphasizing the transition from traditional to constructivist methodologies and examining whether these are truly being applied in today's classrooms. Furthermore, this research analyzes the existing gaps and obstacles that hinder the implementation of the educational reform's proposed approach, as well as seeks and applies evidence to measure the impact of the methodologies currently in use.

Teaching and Education According to Paulo Freire

Paulo Freire is one of the most influential educators of the modern era, proposing that teaching should be understood as a dialogical and liberating process. In his seminal work *Pedagogy of the Oppressed* (Freire, 1970), he critiques "the traditional or banking model of education" (p. 74), in which the teacher deposits information into students who receive it passively. This model perpetuates power relations and suppresses students' creativity and critical thinking. In contrast, Freire advocates for an education grounded in dialogue, where educators and learners collaboratively construct knowledge in a critical and contextualized manner (Freire, 1970).

According to Freire (2005, as cited in Torres, 2018), "authentic education does not occur through the mere deposit of ideas, but through the process of inquiry, in the act of knowing that generates understanding, and in the act of producing knowledge through critical reflection" (p. 91). This approach suggests that meaningful learning takes place when the learner actively participates in their own educational process, fostering dialogue and the transformation of knowledge. Furthermore, Freire (2005, as cited in Torres, 2018) emphasizes that "Freire's dialogical education continues to serve as a key reference in the 21st century, highlighting the importance of the collective construction of knowledge within dynamic and transformative contexts" (p. 91).

Freire's approach promotes critical reflection on social reality, aiming to transform the student into an agent of change. This perspective aligns directly with the principles of the *Nueva Escuela Mexicana* (New Mexican School), as it seeks to overcome traditional paradigms and foster student-centered learning in which learners take an active role in their own educational process. The NEM emphasizes the development of life competencies, holistic formation, and the inclusion of cultural diversity, principles that resonate with Freire's vision of empowering students to engage critically and actively in their learning.

Methodologies

Methodology plays a crucial role within the *Nueva Escuela Mexicana* (New Mexican School, NEM), as it is understood as a set of methods and techniques that teachers must employ in

the classroom to contribute to teaching and learning objectives. According to Alcoba (2012), this methodology “involves the set of teaching methods that the teacher articulates in the daily practice of the classroom, with the method being its basic unit in terms of the combination of techniques and academic activities” (p. 96). This perspective shows that methodologies do not rely on a single technique but rather on the integration of various methods and strategies adapted to the students’ context.

Understanding this concept is essential for the NEM, as it guides teachers through a formative process that ensures the development of methodologies responding to students’ needs and social environments. This allows for the promotion of relevant, dynamic, and contextually adapted education that aligns with contemporary educational demands.

Traditional Methodology

The traditional methodology is characterized by memorization and teacher-centered exposition, and it presents several disadvantages within the educational context. According to Del Vas (2010), its limitations include “a lack of connection with students, the potential for failure if explanations are not understood, and the necessity of maintaining a coherent structure in the teacher’s discourse” (p. 56). Over time, education has evolved through different paradigms that reflect sociocultural advances and transformations. Currently, traditional, behaviorist, constructivist, and socio-critical paradigms are recognized. According to Kuhn (1962), a paradigm is “a set of shared beliefs, values, and techniques within a scientific community” (as cited in González, 2019, p. 26).

The traditional paradigm is based on teacher-centered instruction, in which the teacher acts as the transmitter of knowledge and the student assumes a passive role as a recipient. This paradigm has been associated with rigid, repetitive, and memory-based practices. In contrast, behaviorism, influenced by authors such as Skinner— conceptualizes learning as a response to stimuli, promoting reinforcement techniques, constant evaluation, and behavioral control (Guzmán & Zayas, 2021, p. 33). Within the context of traditional methodologies, students do not develop autonomy or the ability to take ownership of their own learning process. In the educational field, several reforms have incorporated traditional methodologies that, while historically influential, reveal significant limitations in fostering critical and independent learning.

Didactic Methodologies

However, in the pursuit of methodologies that effectively respond to educational needs, the second half of the twentieth century witnessed the emergence of the constructivist paradigm as a predominant influence. Jean Piaget conceptualized learning as “an active process through which the learner constructs knowledge based on interaction with the environment” (Becerra & Morado, 2018, p. 94). This approach acknowledges the central role of the student in the learning process and positions the teacher as a facilitator or guide. More recently, the socio-

critical paradigm has emerged, offering a comprehensive and socially engaged perspective on education. Grounded in the ideas of Paulo Freire, “this paradigm seeks to develop critical individuals who are aware of their social context” (Torres, 2022, p. 61). The socio-critical model focuses not only on what is taught but also on how, why, and from what standpoint teaching occurs, thus promoting the use of active methodologies.

Active methodologies aim to foster knowledge construction, active participation, and cooperative work, all directed toward enhancing student learning outcomes. According to Santana and Feliciano (2006) and Salmerón, Rodríguez, and Gutiérrez (2010), “working in cooperative teams allows students to formulate hypotheses, design steps toward learning, and benefit mutually from the process” (p. 163). Within this framework, the teacher assumes the role of facilitator of learning, guiding and encouraging students’ autonomy in their educational development.

Methodologies of the New Mexican School (NEM)

The didactic methodologies currently proposed are deeply connected to the educational reform of the Nueva Escuela Mexicana (New Mexican School, NEM). Within this curriculum, the document “Methodological Suggestions for the Development of Educational Projects” outlines the methodologies to be applied in this framework. This resource provides a variety of didactic methodologies that teachers can implement in their pedagogical practice.

The didactic methodologies presented in the document include:

- a) **Project-Based Community Learning (PBCL):** This strategy encourages students to engage in projects that have a direct impact on their communities. Project-Based Learning (PBL) can be defined as a teaching and learning modality centered on tasks and characterized by a shared process of negotiation among participants, with the main goal being the creation of a final product. This method promotes individual and autonomous learning within a work plan defined by specific objectives and procedures (Thomas, 2000)
- b) **Inquiry-Based Learning – STEAM Approach:** This approach integrates Science, Technology, Engineering, Arts, and Mathematics, focusing on exploration and discovery. According to Yackman (2008, as cited in Santillán, 2020), “the STEAM methodology contributes to the development of an educational model aimed at bridging fragmented gaps among academic disciplines that have traditionally been separated in curricular development across Science, Technology, Engineering, Arts, and Mathematics” (p. 472).
- c) **Problem-Based Learning (PBL):** This method engages students in solving complex problems to develop critical thinking skills. According to Maturana (1999, as cited in Paredes-Curín, 2016), “problem-based learning (PBL) is grounded in constructivist paradigms, emphasizing the learner’s active role in their own learning process” (p. 125).

- d) Service Learning (SL):** This methodology combines learning with community service, fostering civic responsibility and social engagement. According to Puig Rovira and Palos Rodríguez (2006, as cited in Aznar and Sánchez, 2025), “service learning is an educational approach that integrates learning processes and community service within a single, well-structured project, in which participants develop through engagement with real needs” (p. 120).

Continuous teacher training constitutes a fundamental basis for the strengthening of educational quality, especially in contexts where the educational reality demands a constant updating of knowledge, skills, and attitudes. Thus, it is recognized that teachers are agents of social transformation, as established in Article 3 of the Political Constitution of the United Mexican States, considering that “teachers are fundamental agents of the educational process” (DOF, 2024, p. 1). On the other hand, the General Law of Education (LGE) in Article 86 states that “educational authorities must guarantee permanent opportunities for training and professional development for teaching staff, where relevance, equity, and excellence in the provision of the educational service are considered” (LGE, 2024, p. 45).

From the normative perspective, the National Strategy for Continuous Training 2025 states that “training must be understood as a dialogical, situated, and collaborative process, aimed at strengthening reflective thinking and improving classroom practices” (ENFC, 2025, p. 22). This approach underlines the need to promote formative paths that respond to the needs of school contexts, prioritizing their educational needs.

Mexican School

The New Mexican School (NEM) is based on a pedagogical approach that is shown in the curricular proposal of the model. According to the Secretariat of Public Education (SEP, 2022), this approach encompasses “the organization and the processes that take place in the school, the pedagogical practices in the classroom, and the curriculum” (p. 188). The “School at the Center” approach emphasizes the principle of inclusive education with equity, recognizing that for its effective implementation, it is necessary that all elements of the educational model, curriculum, principals, teachers, parents, infrastructure, budget, processes, information flows, among others, are aligned and respond to this principle.

According to the SEP (2022, p. 20), the new model states that the solution to educational challenges lies in “promoting a more active, self-regulated, goal-oriented, situated, and collaborative learning that facilitates the personal construction of meanings and knowledge.” In this context, four key pedagogical approaches are proposed: deep learning, meaningful learning, situated learning, and socio-emotional learning.

These approaches are currently fundamental for the transformation of educational practice, as they promote teaching that considers the socio-emotional elements and the context of the

students. Understanding the NEM is crucial for research, since the methodologies implemented in the classroom must comply with the educational model, which seeks an education that is inclusive, equitable, and relevant for all students, thus preparing new generations to face the challenges of the contemporary world.

Pedagogical Principles

The New Mexican School (NEM) has a structure that is based on principles which guide its pedagogical approach and its educational objectives. Among these principles, the promotion of identity with Mexico stands out. According to the Secretariat of Public Education, “culture can currently be considered as the set of distinctive, spiritual and material, intellectual and emotional features that characterize a society or a social group” (SEP, 2022, p. 32). On the other hand, within these principles, the teaching work in the NEM is based on guiding principles; these emphasize the right to education of girls, boys, adolescents, and young people as active subjects in the development of their potentialities.

These and other principles mentioned by the SEP are the basis of the NEM educational model and reflect a commitment to the construction of a new school that considers inclusive, equitable, and quality education, oriented towards the formation of citizens committed to their environment and capable of contributing to social well-being. This will be fundamental to understand and analyze, since the aim will be to identify the methodology that fosters an educational environment that promotes the development of students.

Materials and Methods

The type of research developed was carried out with a qualitative approach in order to obtain data, facts, and subjects of the phenomenon known as the New Mexican School. “Qualitative research focuses on understanding social phenomena from the perspective of the participants, using methods such as interviews, observation, and documentary analysis to construct contextual meanings” (Hernández-Sampieri & Mendoza, 2018, p. 423).

Therefore, this qualitative research will be of a phenomenological type, considering that the reality of the classrooms must be studied, captured, and understood. Thus, “Phenomenology, since the twentieth century, has been one of the philosophical currents that has most influenced the social and human sciences, offering methodological tools to understand the lived experience of subjects” (Romero, 2012, cited in Romero et al., 2018, p. 11). For this reason, it is intended to understand the perspectives behind a theory, considering the personal experiences of teachers in service. Taking this into account, an instrument was developed that can explore the meanings and lived experiences within this field.

Likewise, through this approach, stable, reliable, and consistent results are sought, carrying out a triangulation of data and theories, using various data sources and multiple perspectives to interpret what is obtained. For its part, the main objective in choosing this type of research

is to be able to describe and understand each of the teachers' experiences when facing the implementation of the NEM in their pedagogical practices.

The main technique established within the research instrument is data collection based on a semi-structured interview. The semi-structured interview allows the researcher to address key topics through guiding questions, without limiting the possibility for the interviewee to expand their answers or introduce new relevant topics (Hernández-Sampieri & Mendoza, 2018, p. 456).

Questions were designed to guide an interview so that teachers could express their experiences, opinions, and reflections on their use of the New Mexican School and their own pedagogical methodology within the classroom. As such, the interviews have a structure and a purpose, which is to understand the interviewee's perspective and to break down the meanings of their experiences. This is used in favor of describing the situation and briefly explaining the purpose of this research.

The population considered by convenience consisted of ten in-service primary school teachers from the state of Chihuahua, who are therefore the participants of this research. Teachers from this level and this region were chosen as the population due to their training process and curricular design, in addition to having textbooks and the theoretical proposal of the New Mexican School methodology. Within the teaching population, an intentional sample of teachers was selected who were willing to share their experiences and reflections on implementation and their pedagogical practice regarding the NEM, taking into account both state and federal schools.

Results

The analysis of the data is carried out through a process of coding the interviews, using qualitative data analysis techniques through the Atlas.Ti platform, 9th edition, using the data collected through recorded and written interviews, in order to identify themes and patterns through semantic networks. With this, a coherent narrative is constructed that allows understanding the experience of teachers, the use of the NEM, and its impact within pedagogical practices, as well as the relevance between teaching and learning styles.

Research Results on Barriers in the Implementation of the NEM

Figure 1. Semantic network, category of barriers.

Source: Personal creation (2025)

The New Mexican School (NEM) represents a change in the educational context of Mexico, promoting education under approaches of inclusion and humanism. However, its implementation has faced multiple barriers that have hindered its application in classrooms. These barriers range from a lack of clarity in the curriculum to deficiencies in teacher training, scarcity of technological resources, and resistance to change on the part of different educational actors. The objective of this analysis is to identify and describe the main barriers that obstruct the proper implementation of the New Mexican School.

One of the key points in the implementation of a plan and program is the organization of the contents; however, barriers were identified related to the lack of a clear structure in the program offered by the NEM, as well as the excess or scarcity of content and the lack of time to address each of them effectively. Likewise, the administrative overload and the number of students per classroom make it difficult to plan a didactic framework and to apply innovative strategies and methodologies. One of the main innovations of the NEM is to offer greater autonomy to teachers in the organization of the assigned contents.

However, this freedom also represents a barrier when there is no plan with a clear structure and an excess of freedom in the co-design of contents and processes of development and learning (PDA). Some teachers have expressed their concern about the overload of contents in certain formative fields, while in others they observe gaps in the basic contents, such as reading, writing, and mathematical skills, which make it difficult to ensure continuity in learning. In addition, the time available to develop these contents is limited due to various factors such as the number of students per classroom and the administrative workload imposed on teachers, as well as the lack of knowledge about how to develop an analytical plan.

According to Murillo and Krichesky (2021), “teachers face difficulties when programs lack a clear sequence, which impacts pedagogical planning and the application of active

methodologies” (p. 15). In addition, Bolívar (2022) points out that “administrative overload limits the time available for innovations in teaching” (p. 22).

Figure 2. Semantic network, category of barriers.

Source: Personal creation (2025)

Another barrier is the lack of uniformity in the way schools adopt the NEM. While some institutions have managed to adapt efficiently, others face confusion and lag in the methodologies proposed by the program. This has created a gap in the quality of education provided in the different contexts of the country. The lack of an established plan and the constant changes in educational reforms have generated uncertainty in the educational community, in addition to the fact that the priorities of the plan and program are not always aligned with the real needs of students, teachers, and the context in which they develop. As such, the process of adaptation to the new educational programs has been another of the major barriers of the NEM and educational communities.

According to Escudero (2020), “the absence of structured planning causes resistance and difficulties in curricular adaptation” (p. 10). Likewise, Martínez (2021) warns that educational reforms without clear guidelines generate confusion and disorganization among teachers (p. 45). In this sense, some teachers have expressed that the guidance offered about the NEM has been insufficient or consequently unclear. This has generated confusion in the way of applying the principles of the new model, which in turn affects the way students receive and process information.

Likewise, information was collected on the lack of knowledge of the program in the implementation of the NEM among high-ranking authorities, which turns into insufficient training at both the teaching and institutional level. Aspects such as traditionalism, lack of

information, and lack of knowledge about programs and materials limit the appropriation of the educational model. According to González and Guerra (2022), “the lack of continuous training affects the application of innovative models” (p. 60), while Fullan (2020) points out that “educational leadership is key for the successful implementation of educational reforms” (p. 70). In addition, there is a gap between the expectations of the NEM and the reality of teachers in classrooms. Many teachers have pointed out that although the proposal of the NEM is interesting, its application becomes complicated when there is no institutional support, knowledge, or adequate resources to implement it.

On the other hand, it was observed that one of the barriers has been the use of technologies, since teachers face limitations in their infrastructure, access to ICT, and training in their management. Likewise, the lack of adequate materials and the constant updating of textbooks, whose contextualization according to interviewed teachers is far from the reality of the students, hinder the adaptation of projects to the needs of classrooms. In addition, teachers face difficulties in training themselves in the use of new technologies, which prevents them from taking full advantage of the available digital resources. According to Area-Moreira (2021), “the integration of ICT in education depends on teacher training and the availability of resources” (p. 18).

In addition, Cabero and Marín (2023) state that “didactic materials must be adapted to local contexts to be effective” (p. 45). The same occurs with the integration of technologies, which, without adequate planning, end up being ignored in the educational process. Another problem is the lack of contextualized materials for each region of the country. The updating of textbooks has generated debate, as some teachers consider that the new materials do not fit the realities of their communities, making their application within the classroom difficult.

Finally, within this category, resistance to change has been the greatest barrier observed. Resistance to change by students, as well as by parents, represents a challenge in the implementation of the NEM. In many of the observed situations, previous educational approaches and the educational level of the students show a barrier in the transition. Resistance to change is a common phenomenon in any social and educational process, and the NEM shows this type of resistance. In addition, parents play an important role in the acceptance of the NEM. However, some have expressed concern about the lack of clarity and topics addressed in the programs and the impact this may have on the academic future of their children. According to López and Tenti (2020), “resistance to change in education is related to the lack of effective awareness strategies” (p. 20). Furthermore, Molina (2021) mentions that “student motivation is key for the successful implementation of new educational models” (p. 32).

The analysis of the results of the barrier category reveals that the implementation of the NEM faces significant barriers that have hindered its proper implementation, barriers in terms of curricular organization, teacher training, resistance to change, and school conditions. To achieve effective application, it will be necessary to generate solid training strategies, make

programs more flexible to adapt them to diverse contexts but have concrete content to be addressed, and strengthen infrastructure as well as the provision of materials and technological resources.

Research Results on Difficulties in the Implementation of the NEM

The difficulties associated with the implementation of the NEM as a methodology and current educational program are analyzed below. From the analysis, various problems affecting the effectiveness of the model are identified. One of the main observations is the identification of obstacles in the design and implementation of the educational model. The lack of clarity in the structure and objectives of the NEM generates uncertainty among teachers and higher authorities, which impacts the application of effective teaching strategies. According to Díaz Barriga (2016, cited by Camargo and Hernández, 2021), “curricular changes should not be limited to modifying study plans, but to transforming the pedagogical practices and the meanings that the school gives to knowledge” (p. 89).

Figure 3. Semantic network, category of difficulties.

Source: Personal creation (2025)

Likewise, problems related to educational infrastructure and the scarcity of materials are evidenced. According to UNESCO (2022), the lack of adequate resources limits the application of innovative methodologies and hinders equity in access to quality education. This reinforces the need for public policies to prioritize investment in school resources and teacher training (p. 28). Another important point is the resistance to change within educational institutions. The implementation of a new school program implies modifications in planning and in the evaluation of learning, which generates rejection in some sectors of the educational community. According to Fullan and Hargreaves (2018), “resistance to

change in education is a common phenomenon when reforms are not accompanied by clear training and support strategies” (p. 35).

On the other hand, the analysis reveals that teachers face multiple challenges in the application of the NEM, such as the lack of specific training on the NEM. The transition to a new educational model requires teacher updating programs that allow the understanding of the pedagogical and methodological foundations of the change. According to Tenti (2019), “the absence of adequate training generates insecurity and difficulties in applying strategies aligned with the NEM” (p. 77). The excessive administrative workload forces teachers to balance lesson planning with the administrative tasks imposed by educational authorities and the educational context.

Figure 4. Semantic network, category of difficulties.

Source: Personal creation (2025)

According to Schmelkes (2020), “this excess of bureaucracy reduces the time available for pedagogical innovation and individualized attention to students” (p. 40). On the other hand, there are difficulties in assessing learning under the new criteria. The NEM promotes a formative assessment approach (a process of observing the trajectory of learning achievement), which represents a challenge for teachers accustomed to traditional models, as well as for classroom contexts with excessive student enrollment. According to Stobart (2018), “changes in assessment systems require a period of adjustment and continuous training to ensure their correct application” (p. 91).

Finally, the analysis of results also highlights difficulties related to students and their learning process within the framework of the NEM. Within the analysis, inequality in learning conditions stands out; factors such as socioeconomic context, limited access to technology, and lack of family support negatively impact students’ academic development. Various

studies have shown that socioeconomic conditions are key determinants in school performance (OECD, 2021, p. 18). Likewise, the NEM seeks to address diversity in classrooms, but the implementation of inclusive strategies continues to show deficiencies.

To improve the effectiveness of the model, it is necessary to strengthen teacher training, ensuring constant and accessible training on the NEM and its methodologies, as well as to reduce the administrative workload of teaching staff, allowing teachers to focus their efforts on teaching and accompanying students. On the other hand, it is necessary to improve infrastructure and the distribution of educational materials, ensuring that all students have access to adequate resources for their learning. Finally, it is necessary to adjust assessment strategies so that teachers can correctly apply the new approaches to learning evaluation.

Research Results on Strengths in the Implementation of the NEM

Figure 5. Semantic network, category of strengths.

Source: Personal creation (2025)

This analysis highlights the main strengths of the model, such as the emphasis on socio-emotional well-being, the application of innovative methodologies, the contextualization of learning, and curricular flexibility. Based on a review through interviews about its implementation, it examines how these elements promote meaningful, dynamic, and needs-based learning for students. One of the main findings of this research is that the NEM is based on a humanistic and socio-emotional approach; this model prioritizes the emotional well-being of the student, promoting confidence and the free exchange of ideas in the classroom.

Figure 6. Semantic network, category of strengths.

Source: Personal creation (2025)

The centrality of the student in their learning process is another key characteristic. It is observed that students not only receive knowledge but also construct their own learning through creativity, reflection, and critical thinking, something that the NEM seeks to promote through active methodologies. Likewise, the model fosters the development of collaborative and responsible skills; this is reflected in the importance of teamwork and peer interaction. According to Dillenbourg (2020), “collaborative learning improves problem-solving ability and critical thinking, two aspects that the NEM aims to strengthen” (p. 112).

In addition, research is promoted as a learning strategy, which contributes to the development of scientific thinking and a sense of exploration in students. UNESCO (2019) highlights that “inquiry and critical thinking are fundamental in 21st-century education, as they allow students to adapt to changing contexts and solve problems effectively” (p. 28). Another identified strength is the contextualization of content, allowing students to see the relevance of what they learn in the classroom in their daily lives. This strategy aligns with project-based learning, which increases student interest in the subjects covered. According to Barrón and Darling-Hammond (2018), “project-based learning allows a deeper understanding of knowledge, as students apply their learning in authentic contexts” (p. 45).

On the other hand, the use of innovative methodologies is another positive aspect of the model. Flexibility in teaching practice and content, as well as the possibility of applying varied strategies, allow classes to be more dynamic and engaging for students. According to Fullan (2021), innovative pedagogical approaches, such as competency-based learning and interdisciplinary teaching, increase student motivation and engagement (p. 70). This approach also favors learning autonomy, where students experiment, question, and explore actively.

Finally, the capacity of the NEM to adapt to students’ interests is analyzed. This implies that the curriculum is not rigid but adjusts to the needs of the group and allows greater personalization of learning. According to Tomlinson (2019), “differentiated instruction is crucial to address diversity in the classroom and ensure that all students can fully develop their potential” (p. 91). In addition, the NEM promotes an impact on the community by encouraging projects and activities that strengthen coexistence and students’ sense of social responsibility.

The analysis reveals an educational model with multiple advantages, centered on socio-emotional well-being, the contextualization of learning, the implementation of innovative methodologies, and curricular adaptability. These elements contribute to more meaningful learning and the comprehensive development of students. However, to enhance these benefits, it is essential to ensure the continuous training of teachers in innovative strategies and to promote greater collaboration between the school and the community.

Research Results on Methodologies in the Implementation of the NEM

Figure 7. Semantic network, category of methodologies.

Source: Personal creation (2025)

The research presented reveals multiple aspects regarding the methodologies employed in the NEM, identifying both strengths and areas of opportunity within the educational model. One of the central aspects identified is that the NEM adopts a flexible methodological approach, which allows for the adaptation of pedagogical strategies according to the sociocultural context of students. According to UNESCO (2022), this approach aligns with “the global trend of competency-based teaching, which emphasizes curricular adaptation to student diversity” (p. 28). Authors such as García-González and Rodríguez (2021) state that “methodological flexibility improves motivation and meaningful learning, as it allows the integration of prior knowledge with new experiences” (p. 45). However, the implementation of this model requires constant teacher training and a redesign of evaluation strategies to ensure its effectiveness.

Another important finding is the connection between active methodologies and the development of critical thinking in students. According to Freire (2018), an educational model centered on dialogue and reflection fosters students' intellectual autonomy, aligning with the principles of the NEM (p. 25). However, the effectiveness of these methodologies depends on their proper implementation and the teachers' commitment to designing activities that stimulate analysis and reasoning. The analysis shows that teacher training is a determining factor in the application of effective methodologies within the NEM; although the educational model promotes innovative strategies, the lack of adequate preparation can limit their impact in the classroom.

According to González et al. (2022), it has been identified that “resistance to change, lack of knowledge of new pedagogical tools, and administrative workload represent obstacles to the implementation of active methodologies; to overcome these barriers, it is essential to strengthen initial and continuous teacher training, incorporating learning models and the use of technologies” (p. 60).

Finally, a critical point identified is the absence of a solid process for evaluating the methodologies implemented. Without constant and formative evaluation, it is difficult to measure the real impact of pedagogical strategies and make timely adjustments. Authors such as Fernández and Rojas (2022) propose the integration of formative evaluation systems that allow the collection of qualitative and quantitative information about student learning (p. 102). In this sense, the NEM could benefit from the implementation of rubrics, self-evaluations, and peer formative evaluations to monitor the development of key competencies. The results obtained in this analysis reflect that the NEM is an educational model based on methodological flexibility, the development of critical thinking, and meaningful learning. Nevertheless, challenges remain in teacher training and in the evaluation of the methodologies employed.

Discussion

A recurring issue in the application is the lack of training and effective dissemination of changes among teachers and the educational community in general. Many programs are implemented without providing sufficient training to teachers, which hinders their proper application. According to Linda Darling-Hammond (2021), “teacher training is a key element in the successful implementation of educational reforms, as the lack of adequate preparation can turn even the best proposals into failed initiatives” (p. 34). Likewise, every educational reform implies unlearning habits embedded in the educational system and adapting to new methodologies and new learnings.

Constant changes generate uncertainty and resistance among teachers and the educational community, affecting the effectiveness of implementation. According to Meirieu (2021), “resistance to change does not only come from teachers but also from institutions that make

the implementation of new methodologies difficult” (p. 48). Another observation is that educational reforms are often implemented without an adequate trial and adjustment period. In many cases, immediate results are expected without considering that changes in education require time to consolidate and show significant effects on student learning. According to Bolívar (2022), “the lack of evaluation and adjustment in reforms causes many policies to be abandoned before they can demonstrate their effectiveness” (p. 37).

Furthermore, a common criticism of educational programs is that, in many cases, they are designed by individuals who do not have a deep understanding of the real educational context. This generates plans that do not respond to the needs and problems of the classroom. Educational policies are generally designed from an administrative and political perspective, without the participation of teachers and the educational community in a current and real context. This causes a disconnection between the real needs of the classroom and the theoretical proposals of the programs. According to Hargreaves & Fullan (2019), “the disconnection of programs from educational reality increases the complexity of teaching work, as teachers must adapt content and strategies without having the appropriate tools to do so effectively” (p. 72). The political contrast in educational programs reflects the constant influence of governmental ideologies in teaching, which generates progress and setbacks in the implementation of reforms. The lack of continuity in policies, disconnection from classroom reality, and resistance to change limit the effectiveness of educational programs.

Although there is recognition of the principles of the new paradigm and the innovative methodologies proposed, in school reality traditional methodologies still predominate, centered on exposition and control of content by teachers. This gap evidences the transition between constructivist and traditional approaches, which is still hindered by institutional, contextual, and educational factors regarding the creation of educational programs and their relationship with educational reality. The analysis revealed that the main barriers are found in the structure of the program, such as curricular rigidity and freedom, lack of resources, social inequalities, and limited teacher training, which continue to create barriers to the effective appropriation of the principles of the NEM.

Added to this are difficulties in the program’s operability caused by adverse school conditions, administrative overload, and the lack of articulation and effectiveness between school and community. These obstacles have limited pedagogical innovation and highlight the need to create contextualized educational policies with effective pedagogical training support, taking into account the minimum material conditions for real implementation. Even so, it is noted that the NEM educational model offers strengths, among them greater methodological and curricular flexibility, the promotion of critical and reflective thinking, collaboration and reflection, as well as the contextualization of learning.

Conclusions

The characteristics of this educational program, if accompanied by continuous teacher training and relevant evaluation processes, could result in a meaningful, inclusive, and

transformative educational experience. On the other hand, a critical aspect identified in this analysis is the absence of an effective process for evaluating educational plans and programs, as well as the methodologies proposed for implementation. The lack of constant formative evaluation systems prevents monitoring the development of principles and approaches to make timely pedagogical adjustments.

Likewise, the analysis cannot omit the political context that permeates any Mexican educational system. Over time, educational reforms have been marked by government changes and the influence of political ideologies, which has generated constant progress and setbacks. Thus, the lack of continuity, resistance to change, and the disconnection between educational policies and classroom reality continue to be factors that hinder the strengthening of the educational system in the country. However, the current focus of the NEM educational plan, based on comprehensive training, socio-emotional education, and inclusion, represents both a challenge and a valuable opportunity for the contemporary needs of society.

Throughout this research, the existing gaps and obstacles that have hindered, from this perspective, the implementation of the pedagogical approach proposed by the New Mexican School were analyzed critically and reflectively through the results obtained. The current educational reform proposes a shift in paradigms toward a model centered on meaningful learning, comprehensive student development, and active, transformative participation of the school community. However, this approach coexists with traditional practices still rooted in the educational system, which generates barriers and challenges for its real and effective application.

One of the main findings of this study is that, despite the innovative guidelines of the NEM, the didactic methodologies that prevail in classrooms continue to be transmissive in nature, according to the observations in the results, with limited student participation and little connection to the social environment. This mismatch reveals a deep gap between the prescribed curriculum and the lived curriculum in real education, which limits the transformative potential of education. Furthermore, limited pedagogical awareness was identified among some teachers regarding the purpose and significance of active methodologies and continuous teacher training, which results in their mechanical or decontextualized use.

Derived from the findings, several key recommendations are proposed. First, it is considered urgent to strengthen initial and continuous teacher training processes focused on active methodologies and the pedagogical use of ICT, with emphasis on their critical sense. It is necessary to ensure material, temporal, and organizational conditions that allow teachers to experiment, innovate, and reflect on their practices. In addition, it is recommended to promote collegial work as a strategy for shared curriculum analysis and the construction of contextualized didactic proposals. Finally, it is suggested to promote educational research spaces from teacher training schools, enabling future teachers to become knowledge generators and not merely implementers of external policies.

The New Mexican School as an educational model holds high potential for educational transformation, based on the development of critical thinking, active participation, and the contextualization of learning. Nevertheless, the educational model faces significant challenges both in its curricular design and in its practical implementation and educational policies. Thus, this research opens possibilities for new studies that delve deeper into teacher support, initial training in teacher education schools regarding the NEM, curricular co-design, and the impact of participatory methodologies on students' actual learning. Only in this way will it be possible to move toward a truly transformative, critical, equitable, and socially just education.

Conflicts of Interest

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References

- Alcoba, J. (2005). *El estilo de la comunicación didáctica*. Ariel Educación.
- Alcoba, J. (2012). *Didáctica y metodología de la enseñanza: Principios para la práctica educativa*. Editorial Síntesis.
- Aznar, P., & Sánchez, M. (2025). *Aprendizaje-Servicio: Fundamentos y experiencias educativas*. Editorial Graó.
- Becerra, M., & Morado, L. (2018). *Constructivismo y enseñanza activa: teorías y prácticas docentes*. Editorial Trillas.
- Constitución Política de los Estados Unidos Mexicanos. (1917, con reformas hasta 2021).
Cámara de Diputados del H. Congreso de la Unión. *Diario Oficial de la Federación*.
- Constitución Política de los Estados Unidos Mexicanos. (2024). Cámara de Diputados del H. Congreso de la Unión. *Diario Oficial de la Federación*.
- Del Vas, R. (2010). El impacto de las metodologías de enseñanza en el aprendizaje. *Revista de Educación y Pedagogía*, 29(1), 155–169. <https://www.redalyc.org/pdf/5043/5.pdf>
- Díaz Barriga, Á. (2002). *Estrategias docentes para un aprendizaje significativo: Una interpretación constructivista*. McGraw-Hill.
- Estrategia Nacional de Formación Continua (ENFC). (2025). Secretaría de Educación Pública. Gobierno de México.
- Freire, P. (1970). *Pedagogía del oprimido*. Siglo XXI Editores.

- Freire, P. (2005). *Pedagogía del oprimido*. Siglo XXI Editores.
- González, C. (2019). *Paradigmas y modelos educativos contemporáneos*. Fondo Editorial Universitario.
- Guzmán, A., & Zayas, E. (2021). *Psicología educativa: Una visión desde el conductismo hasta el enfoque sociocultural*. Editorial Universitaria.
- Hernández-Sampieri, R., & Mendoza, C. (2018). *Metodología de la investigación: Las rutas cuantitativa, cualitativa y mixta*. McGraw-Hill.
- Kuhn, T. S. (1962). *La estructura de las revoluciones científicas*. Fondo de Cultura Económica.
- Ley General de Educación. (2019). Cámara de Diputados del H. Congreso de la Unión. *Diario Oficial de la Federación*.
- Ley General de Educación (LGE). (2024). Cámara de Diputados del H. Congreso de la Unión. *Diario Oficial de la Federación*.
- Ley General de los Derechos de Niñas, Niños y Adolescentes. (2014). Cámara de Diputados del H. Congreso de la Unión. *Diario Oficial de la Federación*.
- Paredes-Curín, J. (2016). *Metodologías de aprendizaje activo en la educación superior*. Ediciones Universidad de la Frontera.
- Pérez, M. (2014). *Estrategias de enseñanza: Fundamentos y aplicaciones*. Editorial Trillas.
- Programa Escolar de Mejora Continua (PEMC). (2019). Secretaría de Educación Pública.
- Puig Rovira, J., & Palos Rodríguez, J. (2006). *Aprendizaje Servicio: Educación y compromiso cívico*. Graó.
- Resolución de conflictos en los centros escolares. (2019). Secretaría de Educación Pública.
- Romero, S., López, R., & Martínez, J. (2018). *Investigación cualitativa en ciencias sociales*. Editorial UOC.
- Salmerón, L., Rodríguez, R., & Gutiérrez, J. (2010). El trabajo cooperativo como estrategia didáctica en educación primaria. *Revista de Psicodidáctica*, 15(2), 161–178.
- Santana, F., & Feliciano, M. (2006). Aprendizaje cooperativo en la educación básica: Una propuesta metodológica. *Revista Iberoamericana de Educación*, 38(2), 159–172.

Santillán, G. (2020). *Educación STEAM: Innovación y creatividad en el aula*. Editorial Paidós.

Secretaría de Educación Pública (SEP). (2022). *Plan de Estudio 2022: Educación Básica*. Gobierno de México.

Thomas, J. W. (2000). *A review of research on project-based learning*. The Autodesk Foundation.

Torres, J. (2006). *La educación en tiempos de neoliberalismo*. Morata.

Torres, M. (2018). *Pedagogía crítica y educación emancipadora en América Latina*. Akal.

Torres, M. (2022). *Pedagogía crítica y educación emancipadora en América Latina*. Akal.

Yackman, G. (2008, citado por Santillán, G. 2020). En *Educación STEAM: Innovación y creatividad en el aula*. Editorial Paidós.

Maturana, H. (1999, citado por Paredes-Curín, J. 2016). *La biología del conocer y del amar en la educación*. Ediciones Universidad de la Frontera.

Acuerdo número 05/04/17 por el que se establece la Estrategia Nacional de Fortalecimiento de las Escuelas Normales. (2017). Secretaría de Educación Pública. *Diario Oficial de la Federación*.

Acuerdo número 08/08/22 por el que se establece el Plan de Estudio para la educación preescolar, primaria y secundaria. (2022). Secretaría de Educación Pública. *Diario Oficial de la Federación*.

Acuerdo número 14/08/22 por el que se establece y organiza la Nueva Escuela Mexicana para la educación básica. (2022). Secretaría de Educación Pública. *Diario Oficial de la Federación*.